

A study on factors that motivate English-majored students at HUFU in speaking lessons

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Abstract

Motivation has a profound effect on the language learning process of students. However, the motivation of English-majored students to learn English speaking skills is quite low at HUFU. Many students do not care and do not invest enough time and effort in learning English, the ability to learn and the ability to use it in the future is low. As a result, they get bored with speaking lessons and find it difficult to learn this skill. With hope that my study would be helpful in finding ways to motivate students as well as improve the quality of learning speaking skills, I decided to investigate this topic. The research is an attempt to investigate the factors affecting the motivation to learn English speaking skill of English-majored students at HUFU. The main purpose of the study is to find out: Motivations of the students at HUFU whose the major is language; Factors that affect students' motivation when learning English speaking skill and then propose some solutions.

Keywords: Motivation, Speaking skill, speaking lessons, English Language teaching

1. Introduction

English is one of the subjects that considers to be compulsory and necessary for the current generation of students. In material and spiritual life, language is the mean to connect the people around the world. People may be different in race, ethnicity; people may survive in a small corner of the world but just with English understanding, they can communicate and interact with anyone who speaks that language. And so, the first difference gap is the narrower language barrier, then we will not be isolated from the world outside us. When we know how to use a foreign language, especially when that language is the common language in the world, the issue of integration and exchange becomes inconsiderable, as the saying of many sections of the magazine: "The world in our hand" Foreign language itself is a culture, so on the other hand, it becomes a very important means to improve its culture. In the globalized world, this is easily seen. Knowledge is increasing transmitting constantly. Knowing a foreign language equips us another door to go out with the outside world. According to Dornyei (2001), he defined motivation as follows "*motivation explains why people decide to do something, how hard*

they are going to pursue it and how long they are willing to sustain the activities” (2001:7)

According to Gardner, learning motivation consists of four main factors. They are: the purpose of the study, the effort of learning, the desire to achieve the set goal and the right attitude to the behavior (Gardner 1985: 50). Thus, according to Gardner, the motivation for studying a foreign language of students is a combination of the persistence to achieve the set goals, the desire to learn a foreign language and the right attitude toward studying that foreign language. Therefore, the motivation of learning a foreign language is the key to the success of teaching and learning foreign languages.

As a student of the English major, the author can see a real situation in learning foreign language of students. That is, learning to deal with teachers, learning to pass exams and tests and learning just to be able to graduate. They do not really have passion and interest in learning English.

From the above reasons, the author has decided to choose the research topic “*A study on factors that motivate English-majored students at HUFU in Speaking lessons:*” The results of this research will show the motivation in speaking English that HUFU students possess, factors that influence students' English speaking motivation and will help students find solutions to motivate them in speaking English.. At the same time, the research results also help teachers develop their teaching methods to motivate their students in speaking English.

2. Literature review

2.1 Definition of motivation

So far, many researchers have done research on the role of motivation in learning a second language, in addition to the mother tongue. The findings suggest that dynamics play a crucial role in whether a second language is successful (Gardner 1985). Highly motivated learners often give good results with high language proficiency. Motivation, however, is something that is very vague, difficult to identify and measure. Dornyei (2001) defines Motivation as one of the functions of thought that governs and controls the movement of people according to their desires. He also said that motivation is the reason why someone decides to do something, how long they will pursue it, and they will overcome the difficulties in doing it. how.

Woolfolk defines motivation as an internal state that governs human behavior (Woolfolk, 2001: 366) and Burden (1997: 19) argue that from the perspective of motivation

perception is the reason why people planning to do something in certain ways, which factors influence their choices. It is also closely related to the limit of everyone's efforts to achieve their goals. At this time, the role of teachers is enhanced, helping learners to make appropriate decisions. Oxford and Shearin (1996: 121-122) also argued: Motivation for students is extremely important because it directly affects the frequency of second language learning of students, when there is a degree of motivation. How much will their proficiency improve, how do they maintain this second language learning? Motivation is therefore a vital element for learning a second language. And to increase the dynamics we need to know what is their dynamics? Dynamics should be considered in the process of learning and teaching English.

2.2. Types of motivation

There are two types of motivation that always coexist when we do anything: the intrinsic and the exogenous. If a scientist conducts research to discover the world, that is the intrinsic motivation; because the discovery of knowledge is intrinsically linked to the act of scientific research. In turn, if they study because they want to gain the reputation of a scholar, they are dominated by exogenous motivation, because there is no really possible link between "fame" and "scientific research". Usually, both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation motivate people.

2.3 Intrinsic motivation

The concept of intrinsic motivation is framed in the Self-Determination Theory of the 70s. This theory was proposed and developed by psychologists and professors Edward L. Deci and Richard M. Ryan and focused The motivation behind human choices is not influenced by external factors.

According to this hypothesis, there are innate psychological needs in the person that cause him to behave in a certain way, without the need for an outside motivation to promote that behavior.

Richard M. Ryan and Edward L. Deci (2006:56) define intrinsic motivation as "an inherent tendency of people to go out in search of novelty and challenges to expand and train their capacity, explore and learn ". Therefore, the only goal or reward sought for intrinsic motivation is to develop one's inner self, or to discover the unknown, gain knowledge or overcome certain qualities. . In this type of motivation, the activity performed is a way of enjoying.

However, intrinsic motivation can be encouraged through some external factor, although we have to be careful about which factors are used, as they can also create the opposite effect.

2.4 Exogenous motivation

Following the external motivations of Ryan and Deci (1999) refer to the activities undertaken to obtain a separate tool for the aforementioned task. The end is no longer the personal satisfaction or enjoyment of the activity itself, but an expected external reward.

External dynamics can occur autonomously or without autonomy, depending on the individual's ability to choose, as there are external motivating activities that can occur as a result of external control.

In this sense, Ryan and Deci propose two examples to distinguish cases of external motivation selected by individuals and those brought about by external pressure. For example, not acting with the same autonomy, a young student learns and does homework for fear of the father's reaction to his results, that another young man trying to go to college has Higher academic reputation. The action is the same and both rewards are external, but in the second case, the student's choice enjoys more autonomy.

2.5 Definition of speaking

According to Chaney (1998) speaking is a social activity where individuals build and share meaning in a given context. Therefore, speaking skill implements communication function. This means that the speaker builds the idea to express, then communicates to the listener by speaking and vice versa.

According to Hornby (1974), speaking is a way to convey the message to others and speaking is a tool to convey the message directly to the listener, even if the listener understands or not. This shows that speaking activity is sometimes in one direction only, the speaker communicates to the listener without reacting in the opposite direction.

According to (Bailey, 2000), speaking is a process of interaction where speaker intend to build meaning through producing, receiving and processing information. Speaking is a quick and effective mean of communication.

2.6 Roles of teacher in teaching speaking

According to Bryne, D (1986) the process of teaching speaking consists of three stages: the presentation stage, the practice phase and the product formation phase. For each stage the role of the teacher is different. In the first stage, the teacher acts as an informant, introduces a topic for discussion, and the teacher needs to present it in a clear and easy-to-understand manner so that students can understand. At this stage, teachers play a central role, so teachers should set aside a reasonable space for this stage so that students have enough time to understand and practice on their own.

The second stage is the practice phase, at this stage the student becomes the center, at this time the role of the teacher is to create maximum time for students to practice speaking, and skillfully coordinate. so that all students in the class participate in speaking practice

At the final stage, the teacher takes on the role of manager and instructor. Students say what they want. In the process of speaking inevitable mistakes. Teachers will need timely tolerance and encouragement because it is important that students are already using their second language as they wish to try to express what they want to convey to everyone.

3. Method

3.1 Research design

The author of this topic research using methods is quantitative, observations and interviews to collect data for his research.

The survey questionnaire was developed and designed to target participants who are English major students and lecturers of English-department at HUFU.

The main data source used for the research is the results obtained from the survey questionnaire, direct interviews are conducted with the purpose of adding the authenticity to the results obtained from survey questionnaire.

3.2. Research participants

Number of participants involving in the questionnaire survey include 40 students and four English teachers. These students have studied English for at least three years in high school. When participating in the research, they are students majoring in English at HUFU University. According to the researchers' observations, their English proficiency level and motivation level are quite equal. Four teachers of the school have been selected to obtain objective data. They have at least two years of teaching. The results from these teachers will give an objective view of the students'

motivation in speaking.

All participants participated in the survey by answering three types of questions, two for students and one for teachers.

3.3. Instrument

3.3.1. Questionnaire

In this study, quantitative research method is used to find out the Factors affecting motivation in learning English speaking of students major in English at HUFU University. The author decides to select survey techniques to collect data. The instruments to help authors gather information is a questionnaire.

- *Questionnaires for students*

The questions were ed with two main parts: Part 1 Participant's information. Part 2 would collect some information relating to factors affecting students' motivation in learning English. The questionnaire was designed using a five-point Likert scale. The significant had to rate the item on a scale from 1 to 5 corresponding to the degree that they agree or disagree with each statement (1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = undecided, 4 = agree, 5 = strongly agree).

- *Questionnaire for teachers*

The questionnaire was designed with 5 questions about things need to be done to motivate students.

3.3.2. Interview

The reason why the interviews were designed is that the author can further know the challenges of individuals, from which the findings are more specific.

The interview includes two partly prepared questions whose targets are nearly the same with the questionnaire but they have been changed slightly with the purpose of matching the briefness for a quick interview. The interview questions come with some suggestions to help students answer more easily and comfortably. The questions were presented in English in order that the author can have the possibility to listen to students' English speaking skills.

3.4. Procedures

3.4.1. Questionnaire administration procedures

Questionnaires for students were distributed to 50 students of the English major – HUFU University. When delivering the question, the students were carefully explained by the instructor in Vietnamese how to make the questionnaire. Students

have about 10 (ten) minutes to complete the questionnaire and return it to the instructor.

Questionnaire for teachers were distributed to 4 teachers of the English major – HUFU University. Teachers have about 15 minutes to complete the questionnaire and return it to the instructor.

3.4.2. Interview procedures.

The author designed two direct interview questions. Five students majoring in English language at HUFU University were randomly selected by the author for direct interview. Interview time is within 10 minutes. The language of the interview is Vietnamese to help the interviewer answer the interview questions most accurately. The interview was written by the author in a notebook and recorded by phone. Then summarize the collected results, supplement the data for the research paper.

4. Result

4.1 Data analysis

The data collected from the questionnaires and the interview were presented. The finding from these results will lead to the suggested solutions to improve motivation English-majored students at HUFU in Speaking lessons. The data is analyzed in this part of the study in the below tables and charts which show the response for the question having in the questionnaire. The interview data analysis will be presented with the collected data.

4.1.1 Data analysis from the students' survey questionnaire

4.1.1.1 Number of years studying English

Question: How long have you studied English?

Figure 16: Years of Studying English

It can be seen from the pie chart that the majority of students participating in the research (71%) spent 5 -10 years studying English, 18% had time to study English for

about 3-5 years and 11% for about more than 10 years. Besides, they have been accustomed to English as a second language for a long time.

4.1.1.2 Questions regarding students' English learning-speaking motivation

Question 1: Learning Speaking in English is not simple for you.

Figure 17: Assess the difficulty of English speaking skill in students

According to the chart above, we see the difficulty of learning to speak in the students participating in the survey is quite different. 45% of the surveyed students said that learning-speaking in English with them was not simple, of which 8% of the respondents strongly agreed with “Learning Speaking in English is not simple for you”. 42% of them said that learning speaking in English for them was not too difficult. Only 13% of English learners are confident that learning speaking in English for them is simple.

Question 2: You want to learn to speak English just to pass the subject exam

Figure 18: Purpose of learning English to pass the tests

According to the pie chart above. Up to 33% of the surveyed students said that the purpose of learning speaking in English is to pass tests and exams (of which 22% of the respondents strongly agree). 22% think that passing exams and tests is only part of the reason they learn English speaking, so they choose "normal". Up to 46% say that they learn English speaking not just to pass exams and tests.

Question 3: You want to learn English Speaking subject because it helps you better communicate with foreigners.

Figure 19: Communicate with foreigners

According to the pie chart, the majority of students surveyed (85%) said their purpose in learning speaking in English was to help them communicate better with foreigners. Only 5% of them think that communicating with foreigners is not their main purpose when learn to speak English. 10% of the respondents said that communicating with foreigners is not their purpose in learn to speak (of which 5% of the respondents chose the "Strong Disagree" answer).

Question 4: You want to learn to speak English to get a job in the future

Figure 20: Get a job in the future

According to the chart, the survey results show that most of the students surveyed (90%) learn to speak English with the purpose of being able to get a good job after graduation. Of which 66% of respondents strongly agree with the researcher's question. Only 10% of them say that learning speaking in English doesn't aim to get a good job in the future. There is no one neutral, no opinion on this question.

Question 5: Speaking skill is important to you

Figure 21: The importance of learning speaking in English for students

According to the chart above shows, the vast majority of students surveyed (87%) said that English speaking skill are important for them. 3% of respondents said their English speaking skill are not so important for them. Up to 10% of them said that speaking skill were not important for them (of which 5% chose the answer "Strong Disagree").

Question 6: You are gifted in learning to speak English.

Figure 22: Gift in learning to speak English.

According to the chart above, 29% of the students surveyed said they thought they they were gifted in speaking English (of which 5% of the respondents chose the “strongly agree” answer). Up to 53% of respondents said that they are not too gifted in speaking English, but only in the normal level. 18% of them said they did not have gifted in speaking English (of which up to 10% of respondents chose the “strongly disagree” answer).

Question 7: You are serious and focus on learning Speaking English

Figure 23: Attitude of students when learning English

The results of question 7 shows about students' attitudes to learning to speak English. According to the chart above, up to 62% of the students surveyed said that they had learned to English speaking in a serious and focused attitude (of which 11% of the respondents chose the “strongly agree” answer with the researcher's question). 22% of them are not yet really serious and are focusing on learning speaking in English. 16% of the respondents said that they did not learn English speaking seriously and focused.

Question 8: You are interested in speaking to your friends in English in class

Figure 24: Interested in English communication in the classroom

According to the chart above, more than half of the students surveyed (55%) said they were interested in communicating with classmates in English. 34% of respondents felt less interested in communicating English with classmates. Only 8% of them didn't felt interesting to speak English with their classmates.

Question 9: You feel ashamed when you have a speech in front of your classmates

Figure 25: You feel ashamed when you have a speech in front of your classmates

According to the results of the survey of question 9 shown in the chart above, we found that up to 60% of the students surveyed said that they didn't feel ashamed to say or speak a question a thing to their classmates. 31% of them felt normal. Meanwhile 9% of the students surveyed said they felt ashamed to speak or speak in English in class.

Question 10: You feel bored when you are in English Speaking classes.

Figure 26 You feel bored when you are in English Speaking classes.

According to the survey of question 10, only 8% of respondents feel that learn to speaking in class is really boring. 26% of the 38 respondents gave neutral comments on this question and up to 66% of the respondents felt that learning English speaking class was not boring at all.

Question 11: You feel that you have no time to participate in Speaking activities

Figure 27: Time to participate in speaking activities

According to the pie chart above, up to 27% of the respondents said they couldn't arrange a time for speaking activities. 34% chose a neutral answer to this question. Up to 39% of respondents said that they still have enough time for speaking activities.

Question 12: You are reluctant to speak English because the topics is difficult and boring

Figure 28: Topics is difficult and boring

According to the survey of question 12, 18% of the students surveyed said that the topics in English-speaking lessons were difficult and boring for them, making them don't want to speak English. 37% of respondents said that the topics of speech in normal level was not too difficult and tedious. The remainder (46%) told the researchers that the topic was not difficult and boring for them.

Question 13: You don't want to speak in class because the class is too crowded

Figure 29 You don't want to speak in class because the class is too crowded

According to the pie chart above, most respondents (89%) didn't think that the classes were too crowded, so they didn't want to speak English in class. Among them, 42% of respondents seriously disagreed with the answer, 18% chose the "strongly disagree" answer and up to 29% chose "normal". Only 11% of respondents said that the large number of classes made them reluctant to conduct speaking activities.

Question 14: Your method of learning to speak English is not effective

Figure 30 Your method of learning to speak English is not effective

As the chart above shows, 12/38 of surveyed respondents said that their current method of learn English speaking wasn't ineffective to help them improve their speaking skill. 10 people out of the respondents chose neutral answers to this question. Up to 16/38 survey participants think that their current learning-speaking method is effectively helping them gradually improve their speaking skill.

Question 15: Your motivation to speak English decreases because of inappropriate textbook content

Figure 31: Inappropriate textbook content

Survey results on question 15 show how the content of the textbooks affects the motivation of students to learning-speaking in English. As the chart above shows, 21% think that the content of current textbooks was inappropriate for them, which reduces their motivation to learn English speaking. 37% of surveyed respondents didn't think so, because they found the textbooks content suitable for them now. Up to 42% of them choose a neutral answer for this question.

Question 16: You lack goals in speaking

Figure 32: Lack goals in speaking

According to the results shown in the above pie chart, 26% of the respondents said that they lacked the goal to speak English. As many as half of the respondents (50%), in contrast, are still learning speaking in English to pursue their goals. 24% of respondents chose the “normal” neutral answer to this question.

Question 17: Your language learning ability is limited

Figure 33: Your language learning ability is limited

According to the results in the above pie chart, only 34% of the survey participants acknowledged that their language learning ability was limited (of which 5% was equivalent to 2 of the surveyed respondents chose the "strongly agree" answer to express their views). 33% of the students surveyed in contrast, they said that their language learning ability is quite good, without any restrictions. up to 34% of the respondents chose the "normal" neutral response for this question.

Question 18: Teacher doesn't use much English in speaking lesson

Figure 34 Teacher doesn't use much English in speaking lesson

From the survey results of question 18 show that the majority of students (60%) think that their teachers are using English pretty much during English speaking lessons. Only 8% (equivalent to 3 people) of the students surveyed said that their teachers didn't use much English in speaking lessons. Up to 32% of the respondents were neutral, indicating that the teachers' frequency of using English in their speaking lessons was "normal".

Question 19: You don't have enough vocabulary to express your ideas.

Figure 35: You don't have enough vocabulary to express your ideas.

Survey results show that the majority of the survey participants (66%) are having difficulty with vocabulary in learning to speak English, they find their vocabulary is not enough for them to have express, convey their thoughts and ideas to the listeners. 11% of them chose a neutral answer to this question. Up to 23% of the respondents are confident that their vocabulary is enough for them to communicate and convey their message to the listeners.

4.1.2 Data analysis from the teachers' survey questionnaire

4.1.2.1 Teacher's opinions towards students' motivation in speaking English

Question 1: What do you think of the importance of speaking to your students?

Teachers' opinions	Teachers	Percentage
Speaking helps students to improve other language skills and language linguistic knowledge	3	43%
Speaking can bring students enjoyment and pleasure	1	14%
Speaking can help students to broaden knowledge of the world	1	14%
Students can communicate much through speaking	2	29%
Others (please specify):		

All teachers participating the survey considered the importance of speaking activities for students in language learning. 29% of teachers surveyed said that students can communicate a lot through speaking. Up to 43% of them say that speaking helps students improve their language skills and other language knowledge. They think that there is an intimate relationship between speaking and other skills. 14% of teachers surveyed said that speaking can bring students delight and joy and help students

expand knowledge about the world. Only 14% of teachers think speaking can make students feel relaxed and happy.

Question 2: Which stages of a speaking lesson do you find that it is necessary to motivate students?

Stages	Teachers	Percentage
Pre-speaking stage	0	0
While-speaking stage	0	0
Post-speaking stage	0	0
All above mentioned stages	7	100

From the survey results of question 2, it can be seen that all teachers participating in the survey said that they should motivate students in all stages of a speaking lesson. According to them, the role of the teacher is the role that promotes all speaking activities of students.

4.1.2.2 Techniques and activities applied by teachers?

Question 3: How often do you use the following activities in your speaking lesson?

Activities	Always	Often	Sometimes	Seldom	Never
Individual work	2	3	2	0	0
Pair work	2	5	0	0	0
Group work	2	2	4	0	0

According to the survey results of question 3, working in pairs is most commonly applied by the teachers to students during the speaking lessons, however, when working in pairs there is a problem that students willn't have many opportunities to learn from other classmates except from a single partner. The second type of activity used by the teacher is personal activity, it helps students be more proactive and confident in speaking. Finally, working in teams, which comes from teachers often encountering some challenges in speaking lessons such as crowded classes, students who don't want to speak and different levels of proficiency. Setting-up working in teams is necessary. Working in teams give students the opportunity to talk and test for themselves.

Question 4: Which of the following techniques do you use to motivate students to speak English?

Techniques used by teachers	Teachers	Percentage
Combining textbook and relevant materials	0	0%
Giving feedback regularly by marking and giving comments on students' speaking	1	16%
Creating the co-operative atmosphere	0	0%
Applying rewards and punishment	2	28%
Varying communicative activities	2	28%
Encourage them to speak by suggested questions	2	28%

In order to motivate students to learn to speaking, 28% of teachers participating in the survey chose for themselves various communication activities as the main techniques in class teaching. By changing the activities, teachers will give students the opportunity to activate existing knowledge on the subject of the lesson as well as to practice speaking skill. 16% of teachers choose to provide regular feedback by marking and commenting on student speaking. 28% of teachers who took part in the survey considered rewards and punishments to help students talk. 28% of teachers think that encouraging students to speak with suggested questions is an effective measure. Posing students' suggested questions can help students become more involved in the lesson and increase their ability to speak to topics. No teacher chooses a combination of textbooks and other materials, as well as create the learning atmosphere that applies to their lectures.

Question 5: Which of the following speaking activities do you often give your students to do?

Activities	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
Completing dialogue practice	2	3	0	1	0
Picture description	1	3	3	0	0
Story telling	1	0	6	0	0
Rearrangement	0	0	6	1	0
Structure based-activities	1	3	3	0	0
Making up sentences orally	1	3	3	0	0
Free discussion and problem-solving	2	4	1	0	0
Role plays	3	3	1	0	0
Interviews	2	3	1	1	0
Games	0	2	4	1	0

Q& A exchanges	1	5	1	0	0
Visual aids (picture, map, music, handouts)	0	3	3	0	0

According to the survey results of question 5 of seven teachers participating in the survey, it shows that out of twelve speaking activities mentioned in the question, Q&A exchanges, free discussion and problem-solving, role play, making up sentences orally completing dialogue practice, interviews are activities that are frequently performed by teachers. The frequency of using these activities is high because its are appropriate for the student's language proficiency level. The next group belongs to picture description, story telling, rearrangement, structure based-activities, visual aids (picture, map, music, handouts). Most of the teachers who participated in the survey think that these activities will give students a good opportunity to practice.

4.1.3 Data analysis from the interview

** Question 1: What is your motivation to speak English?*

Based on the data gathered from the interview, most students had the same answer: "Have a good job and communicate with foreigners". Some students respond that their motivation to learn English is that they wish they could speak English fluently, and that they always have the goal of learning to speak English well to pass exams and tests with good grades.

** Question 2: What are the factors that reduce your motivation to speak English?*

According to the information gathered in the interview, most students had the answer about the factor that reduced their motivation to speak English due to the lack of vocabulary, which made them unable to express and convey the desired content to the listener. Some students also said that shyness, lack of confidence in speaking English, boring teaching methods of teachers, unattractive talking topics, crowded classes are also factors that cause them to reduce English-speaking motivation.

5. Discussion

5.1. Types of motivation possessed by English-majored students at HUFU

Most of the students surveyed said that speaking skill is an important skill for them (87%). The big goal of the majority of students (90%) who learn to speak English is that they believe that speaking English well will help them to have a good job in the future. Many students (85%) learn English speaking because they wish they could communicate better with foreigners. 33% of students learn English speaking because

this is a compulsory subject in the school and they want to pass tests and exams. Therefore, it is clear that the highest proportion is the student who owns future career orientation and wants to communicate with foreigners. Learning English at the teacher's request because English is one of their subjects at school.

5.2 Factors de-motivating students to speak English

Findings in the research have shown that there are a number of factors that influence and reduce students' English speaking dynamics. Including three factors: factor coming from learners including attitude, teacher factor, psychological environment factor.

The first factor comes from the learners, which includes the learner's attitude in learning to speak English and the language proficiency of the learners. The survey results show that up to 63% of the students surveyed admitted that they were not gifted in speaking English, 38% of them had learned to speak English with an attitude of not serious and lacking. Concentration, although this rate is lower than the number of students studying seriously (62%) but it is still a high number. Lack of background knowledge and inadequate vocabulary to express content is also a factor reducing the English learning motivation of 66% of surveyed students.

The second factor comes from the teachers and the learning environment also has a great influence on student dynamics. In the results collected from the interview, there were students who said that learning was not motivated due to the lack of motivation for the teachers and did not create interest for them, speech subjects that teachers has chosen is not appropriate. Besides, classroom atmosphere is one of the main factors. Most students prefer a pleasant and cooperative atmosphere in the classroom. A pleasant and supportive atmosphere will motivate students and encourage them to participate. In contrast, the atmosphere in a stressful classroom will make students nervous, shy and not confident.

The final factor is psychological, according to the research results from the questionnaire and interview, there are still students who feel shy, timid and lack confidence in speaking English. Although this ratio is much lower than that of confident students who speak English among surveyed students, it is also a factor that cause students to reduce learn English-speaking motivation.

6. Conclusion

Through this research, it can be seen that learning motivation is an extremely important factor that determines the quality and effectiveness of learners. Those who

go to school without goals are no different from those who walk without knowing where to go. Meanwhile, a person who goes to school with a clear learning motivation, but in the learning process, they do not often reinforce and develop their learning motivation, the learning motivation will not play the role. It is also difficult for learners to achieve study results.

Especially in learning communication skills, forming and developing learning motivation in the learning process is a very important issue. More than anyone, students need to be well aware of this issue in order to formulate the motivation to learn in the right direction with strong motivation and constantly motivate and develop that motivation more and more sustainably.

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